

Peritoneal Tuberculosis Mimicking a Peritoneal Carcinomatosis: A Case Report Highlighting the Importance of Histopathological Confirmation

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Abstract

Peritoneal carcinomatosis and peritoneal tuberculosis are two conditions who present clinical and radiological similarities. We report the case of a 69 old year female who was admitted for epigastric pain and vomiting, the EGD with biopsy retained the diagnostic of gastric adenocarcinoma, staging laparoscopy showed peritoneal nodules who were in relation with a peritoneal tuberculosis. In this case we want to emphasize the importance of the diagnostic of peritoneal nodules and the role of histopathological exam.

Introduction

Peritoneal carcinomatosis is a serious complication often associated with digestive cancers, and its appearance significantly affects the prognosis of the disease. In cases of peritoneal carcinomatosis of digestive origin, systemic chemotherapy generally shows limited results. The evaluation of each case should take into account the underlying disease, the patient's overall condition, and the specific characteristics of peritoneal carcinomatosis. Peritoneal tuberculosis and peritoneal carcinomatosis share many aspects that make hard to distinguish between them. In this article we present the case of a patient who presented a gastric tumor with peritoneal tuberculosis.

The Case

We present the case of a 69-year-old female who had undergone a laparoscopic cholecystectomy two years prior. She was admitted to our department with complaints of epigastric pain, vomiting, asthenia, anorexia, and unquantified weight loss.

On physical examination, the patient was conscious, afebrile (temperature: 37°C), with a heart rate of 65 beats per minute, blood pressure of 125/60 mmHg,

respiratory rate of 16 breaths per minute, and oxygen saturation of 99% on room air. Her body mass index (BMI) was 23.14 kg/m². Abdominal examination revealed epigastric tenderness and a positive gastric splash.

Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) revealed an ulcerated, budding tumor in the antrum, highly suggestive of malignancy. A biopsy was performed, and histopathological analysis confirmed the diagnosis of invasive adenocarcinoma.

A thoracoabdominopelvic CT scan showed a miliary pattern in the lungs and gastric wall thickening at the antrum causing esophagogastric distension associated to a suspicious hepatic nodule in the segment V, Biological test showed an anemia with hemoglobin level of 10 g/dL, albumin at 33 g/L, Na⁺ at 140 mEq/L, K⁺ at 4.1 mEq/L, urea at 0.27 g/L, and creatinine at 7.3 mg/L.

The patient's case was reviewed during a multidisciplinary team meeting. The consensus was to proceed with an exploratory laparoscopy combined with the placement of a feeding jejunostomy, followed by chemotherapy.

More Information

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Figure 1: CT Scan Images Showing Pulmonary Miliary and the Antral Thickening with a Suspicious Hepatic Nodule in the Segment V

During laparoscopy, an 8 cm tumor was observed in the antral region, along with multiple peritoneal nodules (Figure 2), which were biopsied. Several hepatic nodules were also identified (Figure 3). A feeding jejunostomy was subsequently performed.

Histopathological examination of the biopsied tissue revealed epithelioid and giant cell granulomas with caseous necrosis concluding on a tuberculosis infection. The patient was discharged on D-1 and addressed to gastro-enterology department where an anti-bacillary treatment was initiated for 1.5 month before starting a chemotherapy.

Figure 2: Image Showing Multiple Peritoneal Nodules

Figure 3: Image Showing Hepatic Nodules

Discussion

Tuberculosis is a global infectious disease that can affect multiple body sites. Although effective anti-tubercular treatments are available, managing the disease remains a daily challenge for medical teams due to the high incidence of drug resistance, the prolonged duration of treatment, and numerous potential side effects.

Peritoneal carcinomatosis refers to the spread of tumor cells throughout the peritoneal cavity, where they disseminate via peritoneal fluid and implant on peritoneal surfaces. This condition can result from primary tumors such as pseudomyxoma peritonei or mesothelioma. It presents in various forms, ranging from microscopic tumor cells within the peritoneal fluid to visible nodules and large masses.

Peritoneal tuberculosis typically manifests in three major forms:

1. Ascitic form – characterized by a large accumulation of ascitic fluid.
2. Plastic form – involves fibrous adhesions and nodular formations on the peritoneum.
3. Fibrotic form – characterized by the formation of mesenteric, omental and peritoneal masses [1-2]

The two conditions – peritoneal carcinomatosis (PC) and peritoneal tuberculosis (PTB) – often present with similar clinical and radiological features, making differentiation between them challenging. On imaging, particularly CT scans, there are many overlapping findings observed in both conditions [3–4], including:

- Ascites
- Enlarged lymph nodes, typically with a hypodense center and a hyperdense rim, which may also show calcifications
- Thickening of the mesentery and omentum
- Uniform and regular thickening of the peritoneum
- Agglutination of intestinal loops

Cancer patients have an increased risk of developing active tuberculosis. This elevated risk is believed to result from a combination of factors, including compromised immune defenses, the immunosuppressive effects of cancer itself, and the impact of treatments such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy [5].

Conversely, patients with tuberculosis may also have a higher risk of developing certain types of cancer, as shown in other studies [6].

The coexistence of tuberculosis and cancer significantly complicates patient management due to the complexities of treating both conditions and the

potential interactions between anti-tubercular therapy and oncologic treatments like chemotherapy or radiotherapy. In general, anti-tubercular treatment is recommended to begin approximately 1.5 months prior to the initiation of chemotherapy [7].

Conclusion

Distinguishing between peritoneal carcinomatosis and peritoneal tuberculosis remains a challenge for both clinicians and radiologists. Definitive diagnosis relies solely on histopathological examination. Delayed treatment of either condition can be life-threatening for patients.

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